

On the Mathematical Limitations and Physical Relevance of the F-theory Landscape

Yusuke Kimura¹

¹*Analytical quantum complexity RIKEN Hakubi Research Team,
RIKEN Center for Quantum Computing (RQC),
2-1 Hirosawa, Wako, Saitama 351-0198, Japan*

Abstract

It is shown that a generic point in the complex structure moduli space of elliptically fibered Calabi–Yau 4-folds does not possess any gauge symmetry. Consequently, gauge symmetry does not arise generically in the F-theory landscape at the purely geometric level, implying that the appearance of gauge symmetry requires highly non-generic tuning of moduli. Mathematical analysis further indicates that the geometry-physics correspondence underlying the F-theory framework possesses intrinsic mathematical limitations.

Date: April 12, 2026

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1 Introduction

String theory has developed as a candidate theory of quantum gravity. However, since its structure inherently relies on the existence of supersymmetry, the non-detection of supersymmetric particles at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) poses a serious problem for string theory.

There is a branch of string theory referred to as F-theory. In this work, we investigate whether its compactifications yield predictions consistent with phenomenologically viable physics, including the compatibility of gauge sector with particle physics.

F-theory [1, 2, 3] is an extension of type IIB superstring to a nonperturbative regime, where elliptically fibered Calabi–Yau (CY) 4-folds are employed as compactification spaces to describe a four-dimensional (4D) theory. The modular parameter τ of an elliptic fiber is identified with axiodilaton, $\tau = C_0 + ie^{-\phi}$, to realize the extension to the strong-coupling regime.

In the framework of string theory with supersymmetry, strings representing elementary particles can consistently form an anomaly-free quantum theory only in ten-dimensional spacetime. Since this result is not consistent with the observed 4D spacetime, string theorists argue that the extra six spatial dimensions are curled up to become small enough to evade experimental detection. These extra spatial dimensions are referred to as a compactification space

in string theory.

Such a six-dimensional space, together with a formal elliptic fiber whose modular parameter τ is identified with axiodilaton, yields a real eight-dimensional space, which serves as a compactification space in F-theory. F-theory is a twelve-dimensional theory, and to obtain a 4D theory it is compactified on an elliptically fibered CY 4-fold.

F-theory is characterized by the property that the geometric structure of the elliptically fibered CY 4-fold used as a compactification space corresponds to the resulting 4D theory. This property enables one to analyze string-theoretic (or F-theoretic) vacuum solutions, referred to as the landscape, by analyzing the geometry of an elliptic CY 4-fold.

In this paper, we examine three structural aspects of F-theory compactifications. Two concern the 4D theory resulting from F-theory compactifications on elliptically fibered CY 4-folds, and one concerns an F-theory theorem on Mordell–Weil torsion on elliptically fibered Calabi–Yau manifolds:

1. Serious problem in the distribution of gauge symmetries in the complex structure moduli space of elliptic CY 4-folds.
2. Serious problem in the F-theory geometry-physics correspondence beyond codimension-1 structure.
3. An F-theoretic theorem on Mordell–Weil torsion of CY geometries leads to mathematical inconsistencies when applied in 4D and six dimensions.

The 4D F-theoretic landscape has a two-layered structural problem. These two layers correspond to the first two themes in the list. Each layer contains a serious structural issue.

Regarding the first theme, mathematical analysis reveals that, at least at the purely geometric level, generic geometries in the complex structure moduli space of the F-theoretic landscape cannot describe realistic particle physics models. They lack a gauge group or contain only adjoint matter representations. We clarify this mathematical fact concerning the F-theoretic landscape. This point is the central result of this work and is discussed in Section 2.

We also mention, in Section 2.4, an exceptional case where an elliptically fibered CY 4-fold is given by the direct product of two K3 surfaces, $K3 \times K3$, with four-form flux [4]. However, F-theory compactification on this manifold does not yield a phenomenologically realistic 4D model.

Regarding the second theme, while the Kodaira classification [5, 6]¹ applies to codimension-

¹We follow the conventions of the terms for elliptic fibrations used in [7].

1 fibers in elliptic CY fibrations of any dimension, the geometric interpretation of matter fields and Yukawa couplings within the F-theory framework involves higher-codimensional structures in the base, where complex surface-level geometric arguments generally fail. Owing to this complicated mathematical situation in higher-codimension structures in the base, the physics-geometry correspondence is not automatic for matter fields and Yukawa couplings. Furthermore, even for the correspondence between codimension-1 singular fibers and gauge algebras, there is no solid mathematical reason linking the types of Lie algebras and the types of codimension-1 singular fibers. This point is discussed in Section 3.

Regarding the third theme, there is a mathematical problem in F-theory: F-theory arguments assert that the Mordell–Weil (MW) torsion of an elliptic fibration on which F-theory is compactified is identified with the fundamental group $\pi_1(G)$ of the gauge group G [8, 9]. However, certain geometries arise in 4D and six-dimensional F-theory geometric landscapes for which this identification does not hold. We discuss this point in Section 4. Therefore, the F-theory argument in question leads to a mathematical inconsistency. This does not imply that all F-theory arguments are mathematically incorrect, but it demonstrates that the framework can produce incorrect mathematical claims.

We state our concluding remarks in Section 5.

2 Generic absence of gauge symmetry in F-theory compactifications

In this section and in Section 3, Y represents an elliptically fibered CY 4-fold:

$$\pi : Y \rightarrow B, \tag{1}$$

where B denotes the complex 3-fold base.

2.1 Codimension-one singular fibers and non-Abelian gauge algebras

Non-Abelian gauge algebras in F-theory arise from singular fibers over divisors in the base B of an elliptic CY fibration. The Kodaira classification applies and classifies the type of singular fiber over a generic point of such a divisor. This fact holds for elliptic CY fibrations of any dimension, since the local geometry of an elliptic fibration around a generic point of a divisor in the base reduces to the case of an elliptic surface.

However, generic elliptic fibrations in the geometric moduli space possess only a \mathbb{P}^1 with a node or a cusp as singular fibers over a generic point of a divisor. Non-Abelian gauge algebras do not arise in F-theory compactifications on these generic geometries.

Elliptic fibration possessing singular fibers of nontrivial singularity type over a generic point of a divisor imposes algebraic constraints on the complex structure moduli of the elliptic CY fibration Y . As a result, geometries supporting non-Abelian gauge algebras form loci of strictly positive codimension in the moduli space of elliptically fibered CY 4-folds Y .

These facts correspond to the following mathematical property of an elliptic fibration: for an elliptic K3 surface, the base is \mathbb{P}^1 ; therefore, the discriminant of the defining equation generically decomposes into linear factors. The discriminant contains higher-power factors only along special loci in the complex structure moduli space. For elliptically fibered CY manifolds of dimension higher than that of a complex surface, the discriminant of the defining equation generically does not factorize.

Now we explain this mathematical property more concretely using equations. When an elliptic CY fibration admits a global section, it can be transformed into the Weierstrass form:

$$y^2 = x^3 + f x + g. \quad (2)$$

Here, f and g represent sections of the line bundles associated with $-4K$ and $-6K$, respectively, where K represents the canonical divisor. The discriminant is given by

$$\Delta = 4f^3 + 27g^2. \quad (3)$$

For an elliptic K3 surface, since the base is isomorphic to \mathbb{P}^1 , which has a single homogeneous coordinate variable, the discriminant Δ generically factorizes into distinct linear factors. For elliptically fibered CY manifolds of higher dimension, for generic Weierstrass coefficients f and g , the discriminant Δ is irreducible and does not factorize.

This corresponds to the fact that for a generic elliptically fibered CY n -fold with $n \geq 2$, singular fibers at a generic point of a divisor in the base do not have nontrivial singularity type. Singular fibers along divisors in the base have a nontrivial singularity type only when the coefficients of either f or g satisfy algebraic conditions such that the discriminant Δ becomes reducible with a factor of multiplicity larger than or equal to two. This is when a non-Abelian gauge algebra arises. Since this requires algebraic constraints imposed on at least one of f or g , such elliptic CY fibrations correspond to loci of positive codimension in the complex structure moduli space. Physically, this means that vacua with gauge symmetry are nongeneric in the geometric sense.

In brief, conditions are required on the coefficients f and g of the Weierstrass model (2) to support singular fibers of nontrivial Kodaira singularity type, which impose algebraic constraints on the complex structure moduli of the elliptic fibration. Consequently, geometries supporting nontrivial Kodaira singularity types form special loci of positive codimension in the geometric moduli space. Thus, F-theory compactifications exhibiting non-Abelian gauge algebra occupy only special loci of positive codimension in the moduli space of elliptic CY fibrations.

2.2 Mordell–Weil ranks and U(1) factors

U(1) factors forming in F-theory correspond to nontrivial Mordell–Weil rank of the elliptic fibration, where the number of U(1) factors is given by the MW rank.

An elliptic fibration having a positive MW rank also imposes algebraic conditions on the moduli space. This is because having a positive MW rank requires that the elliptic fibration admit a free section other than the zero section, which amounts to a nontrivial algebraic constraint.

Thus, elliptic fibrations with strictly positive MW rank also form loci of positive codimension in the moduli space of elliptically fibered CY 4-folds.

2.3 Generic geometric structure of the F-theoretic landscape

Increasing the rank of a non-Abelian gauge algebra or increasing the number of U(1) factors generally requires more restrictive algebraic conditions. As the total rank of the gauge symmetry formed in F-theory increases, the corresponding geometries occupy loci of increasing codimension.

The appearance of singular fibers with singularity types of rank higher than one along a divisor in the base, such as A_n , requires more restrictive constraints on the Weierstrass coefficients f and g than those imposed by the singularity type A_1 , thereby imposing more stringent algebraic conditions on the complex structure moduli. Consequently, such geometries with higher-rank singularity types correspond to loci of higher positive codimension in the moduli space.

In addition to the discriminant analysis given in Section 2.1, the non-genericity of gauge symmetry in the complex structure moduli space can also be seen in the following manner: The appearance of gauge algebra is also reflected in the Picard number $h^{1,1}(Y)$ of the elliptic CY fibration $\pi : Y \rightarrow B$. The Shioda–Tate–Wazir formula [10, 11, 12, 13] states that the following equation holds when the elliptic fibration Y admits a global section:

$$h^{1,1}(Y) = h^{1,1}(B) + 1 + \text{rank } MW(Y) + \sum_i \text{rank } \mathfrak{g}_i. \quad (4)$$

$\text{rank } MW(Y)$ denotes the Mordell–Weil rank of the elliptic fibration $\pi : Y \rightarrow B$, and the sum in the last term on the right-hand side (RHS) is taken over all gauge algebras. Therefore, the sum of the last two terms on the RHS gives the total rank of the gauge groups formed in F-theory compactification on Y . Since the Picard number $h^{1,1}(Y)$ increases only on special loci in the moduli space, geometries with gauge symmetry occupy only loci of positive codimension in the moduli space, and the codimension increases as the rank of the formed gauge group in F-theory compactification increases.

In particular,

- Even the presence of a single $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ factor corresponds to a codimension-1 locus.
- The presence of a single $\mathfrak{u}(1)$ factor likewise corresponds to a codimension-1 locus.
- Higher-rank gauge symmetries occupy loci of higher codimension.

It follows that a generic point in the complex structure moduli space corresponds to an elliptic fibration with no singularity type along divisors in the base and MW rank zero. Therefore, gauge symmetry is nongeneric in F-theory compactifications on elliptically fibered CY 4-folds, at least at the purely geometric level.

Even the simplest gauge symmetries arise only on loci of positive codimension in the complex structure moduli space.

The geometric moduli space is overwhelmingly dominated by compactification geometries without gauge symmetry. Since vacua with phenomenologically relevant gauge sectors arise only along special loci of positive codimension in the complex structure moduli space, gauge symmetry has no choice but to require highly non-generic tuning of the complex structure moduli.

2.4 Flux and exceptional case

As discussed previously, gauge symmetry arises in F-theory compactifications only along loci of positive codimension in the complex structure moduli. Including flux does not alter the underlying geometric conditions for the appearance of gauge symmetry. The insertion of flux increases the cohomology dimension $h^{2,2}(Y)$, while vertical divisors in singular fibers and horizontal divisors yielding global sections belong to the cohomology group $H^{1,1}(Y)$. In general, the insertion of flux does not increase the singularity type or MW rank, except in the special case where the elliptically fibered CY 4-fold is the direct product of two K3 surfaces, $Y = \text{K3} \times \text{K3}$.

Thus, mathematical analysis leaves no choice but to conclude that, irrespective of the presence or absence of flux, for generic elliptically fibered CY 4-folds in the complex structure moduli, the associated F-theory compactifications do not possess any gauge group, neither non-Abelian nor $U(1)$.

When an elliptically fibered CY 4-fold Y is the direct product of two K3 surfaces, $Y = S_1 \times S_2$, the cohomology group $H^{2,2}(Y)$ decomposes as:

$$H^{2,2}(Y) = H^{1,1}(S_1) \otimes H^{1,1}(S_2) \oplus H^{2,0}(S_1) \otimes H^{0,2}(S_2) \oplus H^{0,2}(S_1) \otimes H^{2,0}(S_2). \quad (5)$$

In this special case, the insertion of flux can increase the middle cohomology dimensions $h^{1,1}(S_1)$ and $h^{1,1}(S_2)$, resulting in an increase in the Picard numbers of the K3 components and hence leading to an increase in the rank of the gauge group formed in the theory.

However, in F-theory on $K3 \times K3$, the 7-branes are parallel. As a result, only adjoint matter representations arise, and chiral matter does not appear. Therefore, this compactification does not yield a realistic 4D model.

3 Limitations of the geometry-physics correspondence for codimension structures in the base

We examine the geometric interpretation of gauge algebras, matter fields, and Yukawa couplings.

3.1 Codimension-1 structure and gauge algebras

The Kodaira classification applies to the singular fiber types over generic points of divisors in the base. If these types admit identification with Lie algebras, the singular fiber types over divisors correspond to gauge groups formed in F-theory compactifications.

However, the identification of these singular fiber types over codimension-1 loci with specific Lie algebras relies on arguments involving strings and branes. There is no derivation based solely on the mathematical structures that establishes this identification independently of the strings and branes interpretation. Since the Kodaira classification itself contains no identification of the Kodaira singularity types with Lie algebras, the correspondence between singular fibers and gauge algebras necessarily relies on additional interpretations involving strings and branes.

There is an unresolved mathematical gap in relating the Kodaira singular fiber types over codimension-1 loci in the base to specific Lie algebras. Since the notion of branes does not possess a fully rigorous mathematical formulation, arguments dependent on brane configurations are not purely mathematical.

However, matter fields and Yukawa couplings involve additional subtleties not limited to the aforementioned mathematical gap. Matter fields and Yukawa couplings arise in higher codimension, where the geometry is not controlled solely by the Kodaira classification.

Before turning to higher-codimension loci, we emphasize a crucial connection between the structural issue in the correspondence between gauge algebras and singular fiber types and a theorem stated in [8] to be discussed in Section 4. The theorem asserts that within the F-theory framework, the fundamental group of the gauge group G , $\pi_1(G)$, is identified with the torsion part of the MW group of the elliptic fibration [8]. However, 4D and six-dimensional (6D) F-theory geometric landscapes include geometries where this identification² is impossible, as we will demonstrate in Section 4.

²This identification is considered only for F-theory compactifications on K3 surfaces in [8], while its exten-

3.2 Codimension-2 structure and matter fields

The intersection of divisors in the base B yields a codimension-2 locus. The enhancements of singular fibers along such codimension-2 loci determine matter fields in the F-theory framework.

However, this interpretation contains unresolved structural issues. While the Kodaira classification applies and classifies the types of singular fibers over generic points of codimension-1 loci in the base in any dimension, the enhancements of the singular fibers along higher-codimension loci in the base are not controlled solely or exhaustively by the Kodaira classification. The structure of singular fibers is considerably more complicated along loci of higher codimension in the base. In elliptic fibrations of dimensions higher than that of complex surfaces, additional mathematical structures generally arise in codimension-2 loci or higher, including the appearance of non-minimal singularities, non-flat fibers, or more intricate fiber structures not captured by the Kodaira classification.

Therefore, the geometric structure associated with matter representations requires analysis beyond the surface-level Kodaira classification. The geometry-physics correspondence for codimension-2 loci in the base is not automatic, and is evidently less automatic than that between codimension-1 loci and gauge algebras. Codimension-2 loci in the base, as intersections of divisors, are interpreted as intersections of 7-branes in the F-theory picture. Limiting the discussion to the surface-level Kodaira classification and applying this limited picture to matter representations appears to overlook the mathematical complexity of the singularity enhancements along codimension-2 loci, while insisting that these loci in the base are precisely the structures where matter fields arise.

Indeed, some elliptic CY fibrations develop non-minimal singularities along higher codimension loci, where the vanishing orders of the Weierstrass coefficients satisfy the relations: $(\text{ord}(f), \text{ord}(g)) \geq (4, 6)$. The fibration may become non-flat along loci of this type, wherein the fiber dimension increases and the Kodaira classification no longer applies. In such situations, the standard matter-curve interpretation ceases to apply straightforwardly, and the underlying geometric structures do not validate or justify brane interpretation of singularity enhancements along codimension-2 loci as the appearance of matter representations. This mathematical fact leaves no choice but to conclude that the geometric moduli space of F-theory contains points where codimension-2 loci do not allow for interpretations, at least in a straightforward manner, as matter curves.

sion to 6D compactifications is only suggested. In such an eight-dimensional situation, the identification does not lead to an inconsistency. This point will also be discussed in Section 4. However, the identification leads to a mathematical inconsistency when applied in 4D and 6D situations.

3.3 Codimension-3 structure and Yukawa couplings

Within the F-theory framework, Yukawa couplings are associated with codimension-3 singularities. However, the singularities further enhance along such codimension-3 loci in the base, and presently the fiber degenerations along such higher-codimension loci in the base of elliptically fibered CY 4-folds are not fully classified.

Thus, in the current mathematical status where geometric structures of higher codimension singularities are not fully understood, establishing a fully rigorous foundation for the geometry-physics correspondence remains considerably challenging. Before the correspondence can be solidified, the structures on the geometry side must be fully analyzed. It is impossible to establish the correspondence when one of the building blocks is incomplete.

Overall, the geometry-physics correspondence in the F-theory framework largely lacks the complete mathematical foundations, particularly for singularities in higher codimension.

4 Mathematical inconsistencies in the gauge group interpretation of MW torsion

We discuss structural issues in the physical interpretation of the MW torsion subgroup of elliptic fibrations on which F-theory is compactified.

As noted in Section 3.1, a theorem in [8] (formulated as Theorem 2 in [8]) asserts that in the F-theory framework, the fundamental group of the gauge group G , $\pi_1(G)$, is identified with the torsion part of the MW group of the elliptic fibration. However, certain geometries arise in 4D and 6D F-theory geometric landscapes where this identification does not hold. We discuss this failure of identification here.

We note that the theorem is formulated for F-theory compactifications on elliptic K3 surfaces (i.e. in eight dimensions) in [8], while its extension to 6D compactifications is only suggested; when limited to this eight-dimensional situation, the identification leads to no inconsistency. We will also discuss this point below. The identification of $\pi_1(G)$ with the MW torsion subgroup is formulated more generally in [9] where it is discussed for F-theory compactifications in any dimension.

Indeed, elliptically fibered CY 3-folds and 4-folds with a section, MW rank zero, no Kodaira singularity types, and a nontrivial MW torsion subgroup can be constructed. F-theory compactifications on such elliptic CY fibrations have no gauge symmetry; therefore, $\pi_1(G)$ is trivial. However, the MW torsion subgroup of such elliptic CY fibrations is nontrivial. Thus, the identification of the fundamental group of the (non-Abelian part of the) gauge group G , $\pi_1(G)$, with the torsion part of the MW group is impossible for such CY geometries.

Such an elliptically fibered CY 3-fold can be constructed as follows: Let S be an Enriques surface and \tilde{S} a K3 surface equipped with a fixed-point-free involution $\iota : \tilde{S} \rightarrow \tilde{S}$ such that $S = \tilde{S}/\langle \iota \rangle$. Consider the étale quotient

$$Y_3 := \left(\tilde{S} \times E \right) / \langle (\iota, -1) \rangle, \quad (6)$$

where E represents an elliptic curve. The projection of $\tilde{S} \times E$ onto \tilde{S} descends to a morphism $f : Y_3 \rightarrow S$, which yields a smooth isotrivial genus-one fibration. The projection $\tilde{S} \times E \rightarrow \tilde{S}$ is smooth with fiber E , and since the action of $(\iota, -1)$ is free and preserves the fibration, the quotient $f : Y_3 \rightarrow S$ is also smooth, with all fibers isomorphic to E . Moreover, $(\iota, -1)$ preserves the holomorphic 3-form on $\tilde{S} \times E$: the involution ι acts on $H^{2,0}(\tilde{S})$ by -1 , while -1 acts on $H^{1,0}(E)$ by -1 , so their product acts trivially. Hence Y_3 is a CY 3-fold. All fibers of $f : Y_3 \rightarrow S$ are smooth and isomorphic to E . Hence, the discriminant section is nowhere vanishing, and the discriminant locus is empty. In particular, there are no singular fibers and no Kodaira singularities. A section $s : S \rightarrow Y_3$ corresponds to a morphism, $\tilde{s} : \tilde{S} \rightarrow E$, satisfying

$$\tilde{s}(\iota(p)) = -\tilde{s}(p) \quad (7)$$

for any p in \tilde{S} . \tilde{S} is a K3 surface, therefore, $\text{Alb}(\tilde{S}) = 0$. Thus, every morphism from \tilde{S} to an abelian variety, in particular to E , is constant. This means the morphism \tilde{s} maps \tilde{S} to a single point in E , which we denote by t , i.e., $t = \tilde{s}(p)$ for any p in \tilde{S} . The above condition (7) then becomes:

$$t = -t, \quad (8)$$

so that $t \in E[2]$. Conversely, every 2-torsion point t in $E[2]$ defines a constant section $p \mapsto (p, t)$ to the projection $\tilde{S} \times E \rightarrow \tilde{S}$, which descends to a section of $f : Y_3 \rightarrow S$. Therefore, the set of sections is naturally identified with $E[2]$. After selecting a zero section, the MW group is isomorphic to $E[2] \cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \oplus \mathbb{Z}_2$. In particular, this proves that the MW rank is zero, while the MW torsion is nontrivial.

An elliptically fibered CY 4-fold with no Kodaira singularity types, MW rank zero, and a nontrivial MW torsion can be constructed similarly. Let B be a 3-fold with torsion canonical bundle, and let \tilde{B} be its étale double cover equipped with a nowhere-vanishing holomorphic 3-form and a fixed-point-free involution $\kappa : \tilde{B} \rightarrow \tilde{B}$ such that $B = \tilde{B}/\langle \kappa \rangle$. Assume moreover that $h^{1,0}(\tilde{B}) = 0$ (equivalently, $\text{Alb}(\tilde{B}) = 0$). Then, the quotient

$$Y_4 := \left(\tilde{B} \times E \right) / \langle (\kappa, -1) \rangle, \quad (9)$$

yields the desired CY 4-fold equipped with a smooth isotrivial elliptic fibration $Y_4 \rightarrow B$. As in the 3-fold case, all fibers are smooth over the base 3-fold B , so the discriminant section is nowhere vanishing and the discriminant locus is empty; in particular, there are no Kodaira singularities. An argument analogous to the above shows that the MW group $\text{MW}(Y_4/B)$ is isomorphic to $E[2] \cong \mathbb{Z}_2 \oplus \mathbb{Z}_2$, so the MW rank is zero while the MW torsion is nontrivial.

As an explicit construction of such a base 3-fold B , take $\tilde{B} = Y_3$, where Y_3 is the CY 3-fold constructed above. Recall that Y_3 is an étale quotient of $\tilde{S} \times E$. Let $a \in E[2]$ be a nonzero 2-torsion point, and consider the involution (ι, t_a) on $\tilde{S} \times E$, where t_a represents translation by a . Since a is in $E[2]$, this involution satisfies $(\iota, t_a)^2 = \text{id}$, commutes with $(\iota, -1)$, and is fixed-point free. Hence it descends to a fixed-point-free involution on Y_3 , which we denote by κ . Defining $B := Y_3/\langle\kappa\rangle$, we obtain a 3-fold with torsion canonical bundle. Indeed, the involution κ acts on the holomorphic 3-form of Y_3 by -1 , so K_B is nontrivial but 2-torsion, and $\tilde{B} = Y_3$ is its étale double cover with trivial canonical bundle.

Thus, we have demonstrated, by explicit constructions, that 4D and 6D F-theory geometric landscapes contain geometries where the identification of the fundamental group of the (non-Abelian part of the) gauge group G , $\pi_1(G)$, with the torsion part of the MW group fails. For these geometries, the aforementioned F-theory theorem identifying $\pi_1(G)$ with the MW torsion subgroup cannot be valid.

This mismatch leaves no choice but to conclude that the proposed correspondence, as formulated in F-theory, between gauge group data and the underlying elliptic fibration cannot be consistently maintained in full generality.

We note that this situation does not occur for elliptic K3 surfaces with a global section. Indeed, Theorem 2.14 in [14] asserts that when $\text{rank} \sum_i \mathfrak{g}_i \leq 7$ (the notation $\text{rank}(\Sigma_f)$ is used for $\sum_i \mathfrak{g}_i$ in [14]), the MW torsion subgroup must be trivial. When singular fiber types over generic points of the divisors in the base are all either I_1 or II , $\sum_i \mathfrak{g}_i = 0$, and therefore the MW torsion subgroup must be trivial. This means that whether one can consistently identify $\pi_1(G)$ with the torsion part of the MW group is inherently dimension-dependent. In particular, this indicates that the identification is not a universal feature of F-theory compactifications, but rather holds under restrictive conditions. In eight dimensions, the identification is possible; however, in 4D and 6D, the identification becomes impossible for some geometries.

The breakdown of the identification of the fundamental group of the gauge group G , $\pi_1(G)$, with the torsion part of the MW group poses multiple structural issues in the correspondence between the mathematical structure of elliptic fibrations and their interpretation as global gauge group structure. We summarize the main structural issues implied by this breakdown as follows:

- While MW torsion exists, there is no gauge group for it to act on. This suggests that the F-theory framework may overcount the geometric and arithmetic structure of elliptic fibrations as physical.
- Whether the identification is physically sensible is dimension-dependent, which implies that the identification is not universally justifiable.

- MW torsion cannot be identified with a discrete gauge symmetry, since the Tate–Shafarevich (TS) group of a genus-one fibration lacking a global section but with an n -section has an interpretation as a discrete gauge symmetry [15].
- One may argue that a model with no gauge group but with nontrivial MW torsion results from Higgsing of a model with a gauge group and nontrivial MW torsion. However, not every geometric deformation removing Kodaira singularities while maintaining MW torsion is physically allowed, particularly in 4D and 6D F-theory. This requires highly nontrivial physical constraints, and the existence of such physically consistent geometric deformations is highly unclear.
- F-theory itself does not appear to possess the ability to exclude geometries in which geometric structures assigned physical meaning lose that physical meaning.

5 Concluding remarks

F-theory was proposed as a nonperturbative extension of string theory, which was once advertised as a “theory of everything.” However, the physical and mathematical analyses presented in this study revealed two layers of structural problems inherent in F-theory.

Mathematical analysis revealed that gauge groups do not form at a generic point in the 4D F-theoretic geometric landscape on elliptically fibered CY 4-folds, irrespective of the presence or absence of flux. Almost all vacua in the landscape possess no gauge group, neither non-Abelian nor $U(1)$, at least at the purely geometric level.

We also pointed out that the Kodaira classification does not generally apply to singular fibers beyond codimension-1 loci in the base B . While the types of singular fibers over a generic point of a divisor in the base are given by the Kodaira classification, the classification does not apply to those over loci of higher codimension. Since matter fields and Yukawa couplings pertain to loci of codimension-2 and codimension-3, respectively, the physics-geometry correspondence for these structures is not automatic. Simplistic physical interpretations of such higher-codimension loci lack a solid mathematical foundation.

The aim of string theory was to provide a description of phenomenologically viable physics. However, detailed and rigorous mathematical analyses revealed the geometric structure of the 4D F-theoretic landscape as a collection of physically unrealistic vacua that generically lack gauge symmetry. Since the geometric moduli space is overwhelmingly dominated by compactification geometries without gauge symmetry and realistic gauge sectors appear in F-theory only along special loci of positive codimension in the complex structure moduli, the appearance of gauge symmetry in F-theory has no choice but to require highly non-generic moduli tuning as restrictions to special measure-zero loci in the geometric moduli space.

The moduli space of elliptically fibered CY 4-folds is extremely vast. A statistical study of flux vacua in F-theory would therefore yield the result that a generic member of the whole ensemble has no gauge symmetry, when studied with full generality. When statistical studies restrict attention to a highly constrained subset of compactifications, the nongeneric nature of gauge symmetry may not be explicitly visible, since such a restricted study does not represent the full ensemble. Since such statistical studies focus only on restricted patches of the geometric moduli space, their implications for the full F-theoretic landscape remain unclear.

In summary, the analyses presented in this study revealed the following four serious problems inherent in the F-theory framework:

1. Generic compactification geometries lack gauge symmetry.
2. The identification between singular fiber types and gauge algebras is not derived purely from the mathematical structure.
3. Matter and Yukawa couplings do not follow automatically from higher-codimension geometry.
4. Certain F-theoretic arguments have led to mathematical inconsistencies in 4D and 6D theories, implying that the proposed correspondence between gauge group data and the mathematical structure of elliptic fibrations is not internally consistent.

Acknowledgments

Y.K. acknowledges Hakubi projects of RIKEN. This work was supported by the JSPS Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research, No. JP24K06909.

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